

Pharmacological Potential of Chromone-Based Heterocycles: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Compounds bearing the Chromone derivatives provide a versatile platform for chemical synthesis due to the presence of a highly reactive carbonyl group. They are of considerable importance because of their significant and varied biological activities and their pronounced reactivity toward nucleophiles, enabling the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic systems. Chromones and their derivatives are widespread in nature. Chromones from both natural origins and synthetic routes are crucial in life science research. The activities associated with Chromone nucleus are antitumor, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, oestrogenic and antibacterial. Chromone derivatives bearing heterocyclic substituents at the 2-position are known to display a wide range of biological activities, including antitumor, antibacterial, and antifungal effects. In addition, they exhibit good phosphodiesterase IV inhibitory activity, and some chromones have also been identified as potential inhibitors of HIV integrase. Most of these involve condensation between two aromatic precursors.

Keywords: Chromones, Synthesis, Biological activities, Substituted analogues.

INTRODUCTION

Chromones are known to exhibit anti-inflammatory¹, antimicrobial², anticancer³, antiallergic⁴ and coronary vasodilatory⁵ activities. Certain chromone derivatives have also demonstrated potential HIV-integrase inhibitory activity⁶⁻¹⁰. In addition, chromones have been reported to function as fungicides and central nervous system stimulants¹¹.

He, X., et.al.¹² reported the synthesis of 7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid using polyphosphoric acid (PPA) as the reagent. The reaction involved hydrolysis of chromone side-chain esters without cleavage of the chromone ring. The resulting 7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid exhibits significant biological properties, including antiviral¹³ and aldose reductase inhibitory activities¹⁴.

Venkati, M., and coworkers¹⁵ reported the reaction of 3,3-dibromochromon-4-ones with various heterocyclic secondary amines, leading to the formation of 3-substituted chromones. Subsequent

reduction of these compounds with NaBH₄ afforded exclusively cis-3-heterocycle-substituted chromon-4-ols in good yields. The synthesized 3-aminochromon-4-ols have been reported to exhibit adrenergic receptor antagonist activity¹⁶.

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Pandey, A. K.¹⁷ synthesized 2'-hydroxy-4',5'-dimethyl-substituted chromones and evaluated their antimicrobial activity. Chromones moieties are having heterocyclic substituents at 2-positions have been reported to possess antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal activities and also exhibits good inhibition activity while some flavones have potential HIV-integrase inhibition activity.¹⁸⁻²²

Furthermore, chromone derivatives containing 2-pyridyl and 3-pyridyl moieties as heterocyclic substituents at the 2-position have been found to

possess analgesic and coronary vasodilatory activities²³. The biological activities associated with chromones have attracted significant attention in pharmaceutical and medicinal research, these nuclei together with the advantages offered by microwave-assisted organic synthesis, motivated us to synthesize novel chromone derivatives using conventional methods.

Jagadhani S.G. et al²⁴ has Synthesized 2-[1-(4-pyridin-2-ylbenzyl)-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl]-4H-chromen-4-one.

There has been growing interest in the application of microwave irradiation for organic synthesis under solvent-free conditions²⁵. Karale, B. K., and co-

workers²⁶ reported the microwave-assisted synthesis of 3-methyl-4-[(chromen-3-yl)methylene]-1-phenylpyrazolin-5-(4H)-ones using alumina as a solid support under solvent-free conditions.

Nohara, et al.,²⁷ carried out a reaction in which 3-formylchromone when condensed with malonic acid in pyridine form its acrylic acid derivative by

condensation of active methylene group followed by decarboxylation.

3-Formylchromone reacts with cyanoacetic acid²⁸ through condensation involving the active methylene group, followed by subsequent decarboxylation.

Desai, B. M., et al.,²⁹ reported the following synthesis.

Charlton, J. L., and co-workers³⁰ reported the synthesis of ethyl-2-methylchromone-3-carboxylate by the condensation of salicyloyl chloride and the enamine of ethyl acetoacetate.

Gupta, S. C., et al.,³¹ reported the synthesis of spirochromones bearing dihydrofuryls and acylcyclopropanes.

Joshi, N. S. et al.,³² described the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some fluorine containing chlorochromones and chromones.

Varma, R., et al.,³³ reported a solvent free synthesis of chromones, which simply involves the MW irradiation of o-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethanes

absorbed on montmorillonite K10 clay for 1-1.5 minutes.

Miyake, H., and co-workers³⁴ reported syntheses of chromones via the iodine-mediated oxidative cyclization. When 1,3-diphenylprop-2-en-1-ones

were heated with iodine in triethylene glycol, oxidative cyclization underwent to obtain chromones in good yields.

The incorporation of perfluoroalkyl groups or fluorine into the heterocyclic systems, may lead to enhance chemical properties, and biological effects³⁵⁻³⁹. It is also known that catalytic amounts of iodine in DMSO

will accomplish the oxidative cyclization of 2'-hydroxy-chalcones and 2'-hydroxy-2-cinnamylideneacetophenones into 2-phenyl- and 2-styrylchromones, respectively⁴⁰⁻⁴¹.

A one-step synthesis of 3-iodoflavones was reported by Iqbal et al.⁴² using 2'-hydroxychalcones in the presence of an iodine/sulfuric acid/dimethyl sulfoxide system. The synthesis of 3-substituted chromones is of particular interest because they are important natural products, such as isoflavones, and are also

present in medicinal compounds like ipriflavone, which is used as an anti-osteoporotic agent.⁴³⁻⁴⁴

Gammill⁴⁵ described the synthesis of 3-halogenated chromones, which allows the synthesis of a number of new 3-chloro, 3-bromo, and 3-iodo compounds from a common enamino ketone intermediate in good yields.

Sahastrabudde and Ghiya 46 reported synthesis of 3-chlorochromones by reaction of dimethyl sulfoxide and copper chloride with chalcones and flavanones.

Joshi N. S. et al 47 reported DMSO/ CuCl₂ and DMSO/ I₂-Catalyzed Synthesis of 3-Chlorochromones and Chromones and their Antimicrobial Activities.

Bachute R. T. et al 48 reported DMSO/ CuBr₂ and DMSO/ I₂ catalyzed synthesis of 3-Bromochromones and chromones.

Condensation of 3-formylchromone with compounds possessing active methylene groups has been widely reported in the literature 49-52. 3-Methyl-4-[(chromon-3-yl) methylene]-1-phenyl- pyrazolin-5(4H)-one when coupled with thiourea in alcoholic KOH yielded 2-thio-5- hydroxy-5H-[1 benzopyran [4, 3-d]pyrimidines which exhibited remarkable antibacterial and fungicidal activities⁵³.

In recent years, the synthesis and biological evaluation associated with 3-styrylchromones have been reported in literature 54.

A number of novel 3-styrylchromones have been synthesized through the condensation of p-

nitrotoluene and phenylacetic acid with 3-formylchromones in the presence of piperidine.⁵⁵ 3-Formylchromones are known to possess various biological activities such as antimicrobial, antiallergic, and anesthetic properties 56-57.

Ono M and colleagues⁵⁸ reported the development of ¹⁸F-labeled flavones for in vivo imaging of β -amyloid plaques in Alzheimer's disease brains. The ¹⁸F-labeled flavones were synthesized through an aryl ester intermediate pathway.

Liu H et.al. described the synthesis of novel flavone derivatives⁵⁹ and evaluated their antiproliferative activity against hepatocarcinoma (HepG-2) cells. The

desired cromones were prepared via an aryl ester intermediate.

Peng C C⁶⁰ and group have published the synthesis of newer tight-binding inhibitors of cytochrome P450 2C9 via aryl ester intermediate.

Kamal A and co-workers⁶¹ reported the synthesis of 5-carbomethoxymethyl-7-hydroxy-2-pentylchromone, 5-carboethoxymethyl-4',7-

dihydroxyflavone, and their analogues, along with the evaluation of their antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer activities.

Hampson L J and co-workers⁶² described the synthesis of novel flavones through a β -diketone intermediate

and assessed their bioactivity in hepatocytes, demonstrating their ability to bind to the purine site.

Flavones and its derivatives are associated with important physiological activities. DMSO/I₂ catalyzed syntheses of chromones are the reactions of interesting chemistry. Due to the vital role of plant-derived constituents in human life as food materials, agrochemicals, and therapeutic agents chromones have attracted considerable attention because of their diverse and significant biological activities.⁶³ The 4-oxo-4H-[1]benzopyran nucleus, a key structural motif of chromones, gained early interest among chemists owing to its widespread natural occurrence within the flavonoid family. The chemistry of this Benz-annulated γ -pyrone system, along with that of the parent γ -pyrone, has been extensively explored over many decades.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ Recently considerable interest has been renewed in chromone chemistry has largely been driven by their promising pharmaceutical potential.⁶⁷

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